

Synthesis of Some Substituted 5-Thiazolidones for Possible Use as Fungicides

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Condensation of 5-bromo-3-N-aryl rhodanine with phenyl thiourea affords N-aryl-5-(2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidone-5-yl)-thiourea. Further, condensation of 5-bromo-3-N-aryl rhodanine with 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione and with 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-nitroso-2-pyrazolin-5-thione yielded respectively 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(3'-N-phenyl rhodanine)-2-pyrazolin-5-thione and 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-nitroso-(3'-N-phenyl rhodanine)-2-pyrazolin-5-thione. Altogether eighteen compounds were prepared and their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae* was studied. The activity of most of these compounds was well comparable with any standard commercial fungicide.

LITERATURE revealed that 3-N-substituted-aryl rhodanine possesses strong pesticidal¹ and fungicidal²⁻⁴ activity. Encouraged by the biological importance of this type of compounds, we have synthesised some substituted thiazolidone derivatives by condensing 3-N-aryl-5-monobromo rhodanine with phenyl thiourea, 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione and its nitroso derivatives, with a view to study the fungicidal activities of this type of compounds.

Gakhar and associates⁵ reported the synthesis of pyrazolo-thiazole derivatives by the treatment of phenyl thiourea with 4-bromo-1,3-diphenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one. But under the similar condition, the condensation of 4-bromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one with phenyl thiourea gives only N-phenyl-substituted-5-(2-pyrazolin-5-one-4-yl)-thiourea, instead of the cyclised product. The sulfohydryl group of the phenyl thiourea condenses with the 4-bromo-1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one to yield N-phenyl-5-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one-4-yl)-thiourea. Similarly, 5-bromo-3-N-phenyl rhodanine on treatment with phenyl thiourea yields N-aryl-5-(2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidone-5-yl)-thiourea (I). Further, condensation of 5-bromo-3-N-phenyl rhodanine with 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione and its 4-nitroso derivative yields 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(3'-N-phenyl rhodanine)-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (III) and 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-nitroso-(3'-N-phenyl rhodanine)-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (II). When a saturated solution of iodine in potassium iodide is added to the alkaline solution of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(3'-N-phenyl rhodanine)-2-pyrazolin-5-thione, oxidation takes place giving rise to the unsaturated product (IV). The reaction of the synthesis may be outlined as follows.

The structure of all these compounds was supported by their elemental analysis, infrared and mass spectral studies. The ir spectra of compound (I) showed bands near 1720-1710, 1130 and 751 cm^{-1} which were attributable to carbonyl absorption band, C=S stretching and C-S-C stretching vibrations, respectively. Further, a broad band from 3490 to 2050 cm^{-1} arises from NH and enolic OH stretching vibrations which overlaps. The mass spectra of this compound was studied for confirmation of its structure. The mass spectra show the molecular ion peak at 359. The major peaks noticed from the fragmentations at 327, 251, 223 are due to

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the elimination of S(32), CS₂(76) and CO(28) and the peaks at 104, 77 and 27 are for the Ph-N=CH, Ph and HCN, respectively.

In case of compound (II), ir bands at 1700, 1590, 1340 and 1151 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to carbonyl, C-NO, C-CH₃ and C=S stretching vibrations, respectively.

The compound (IV) giving ir bands at 1730, 1600, 1070 and 760 cm⁻¹ are attributable for carbonyl absorption, absorption of C=C in conjugation with carbonyl group, C=S and C-S-C stretching vibrations, respectively. The relevant elemental and fungicidal data of the compounds are enlisted in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—N-ARYL-5-(2-MERCAPTO-3-PHENYL-4-THIAZOLIDONE-5-YL)-THIOUREA

(I)

Sl. No.	R	% Sulphur Found (Calcd.)	% Inhibition of spores at 1000/100/10 ppm	
			<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	C ₆ H ₅	26.99 (26.74)	98/52/20	86/43/18
2.	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(o)	24.85 (24.38)	100/55/24	95/47/21
3.	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(m)	24.73 (24.38)	86/43/16	72/34/12
4.	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p)	24.97 (24.38)	95/51/18	67/28/9
5.	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (o)	23.23 (23.76)	96/54/19	70/35/11
6.	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (m)	23.16 (23.76)	85/46/15	54/25/8
7.	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (p)	23.05 (23.76)	52/29/9	47/22/6
8.	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (o)	24.01 (24.67)	83/44/12	55/26/9
9.	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (m)	24.22 (24.67)	81/45/11	72/31/12
10.	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (p)	24.85 (24.67)	53/27/9	75/38/13
11.	C ₁₀ H ₇ (α)	23.98 (23.47)	76/10/12	65/29/8
12.	C ₁₀ H ₇ (β)	23.03 (23.47)	90/53/14	67/30/9
13.	C ₆ H ₄ Br(p)	22.07 (21.91)	55/30/10	60/28/7
14.	C ₆ H ₄ SN	24.08 (23.76)	44/24/8	52/23/6
15.	C ₆ H ₄ OH ₂ (p)	26.18 (25.73)	95/51/16	52/24/6

All the compounds have high m.p. above 300°.

TABLE—2

Sl. No.	Compound	m.p. °C	% Sulphur Found (Calcd.)	% Inhibition of germination at 1000/100/10 ppm	
				<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	II	330	22.02 (22.53)	98/52/22	76/35/12
2.	III	310	24.90 (24.18)	92/50/20	70/32/10
3.	IV	95	24.95 (24.80)	85/49/16	67/29/8

All the compounds prepared were screened for their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen, *Pyricularia oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae* by standard methods⁶, using spore germination tests at various concentrations. The fungicidal results of compounds (I) are shown in Table 1 and those of compounds (II), (III) and (IV) in Table 2. From the antifungal activity of compound I series, it is seen that except compound with Sl. No. 7, 10, 13 and 14, all the compounds exhibited significant fungicidal activity against *P. oryzae*. Compound No. 2 showed highest activity i.e. 100% and 95% spore germination inhibition against *P. oryzae* and *H. oryzae*, respectively at 1000 ppm. In general, this series of compounds were highly active against these two pathogens. From the results of Table 2, it is seen that all the three compounds were highly active against both the pathogens. One interesting result was noticed with compound (IV) in which the fungitoxicity was found to be unaltered markedly even after the creation of C₄=C double bond which is contradictory to our earlier observations in heterocyclic compounds.

Some of the standard fungicides like O-ethyl-S,S-diphenyl phosphorodithioate (Hinosan 50%) EC, Difolatan 50% WP and Derosal 60% WP, which inhibit 95, 98 and 87% of spore germination of *P. oryzae* at 1000 ppm were included in our study for the comparison of the activity of the synthesised compounds. The compounds 1, 2, 3, 5, 12 (Table 1) and compound II and III (Table 2) inhibit spore germination in the same range as the above standard fungicides. Therefore these may be used as commercial fungicides.

Experimental

N-Aryl-5-(2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidone-5-yl)-thiourea (I): 5-Bromo-3-phenyl rhodanine (0.01 mole) and phenyl thiourea (0.01 mole) were taken in ethanol (25 ml) along with fused sodium acetate (10 g). The resulting mixture was refluxed for 4 hr over a water bath. The excess of ethanol was distilled off. After cooling the mixture ice cold water (20 ml) was added. A deep brown compound precipitated out which was filtered, washed with distilled water, dried in vacuum and finally crystallised from ethanol. Black coloured crystals, m.p. 320°, yield 75%. The compound is soluble in 10% NaOH solution and gives colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-nitroso-(3'-N-phenyl rhodanine)-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (II): 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-nitroso-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (0.01 mole) and 5-bromo-3-N-aryl rhodanine (0.01 mole) were taken in ethanol (25 ml) followed by fused sodium acetate (10 g) and the resulting mixture was refluxed for 4 hr over water bath. The excess of alcohol was distilled off and ice cold water added. A yellow coloured solid formed was filtered, washed with distilled water and finally dried in vacuum. Crystallisation from ethanol yielded light yellow

coloured crystals, m.p. 330° yield 65%. The compound is soluble in 10% NaOH solution and gives colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃ solution.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(3'-N-phenyl rhodanine)-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (III): This compound was prepared in the same manner as II by taking 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione and 5-bromo-3-N-aryl rhodanine both 0.01 mole. Black coloured compound, m.p. 320°, yield 70%. The compound is soluble in 10% NaOH solution and gives colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃.

The oxidation product of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(3'-N-phenyl rhodanine)-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (IV): 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(3'-N-phenyl rhodanine)-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (5 g) was dissolved in 10% NaOH solution (20 ml). To it a saturated solution of iodine in potassium iodide (25 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring. A deep brown coloured compound precipitated out which was filtered, washed with 20% sodium thiosulphate solution and then with distilled water and finally dried in vacuum. Crystallisation from acetone yielded deep brown coloured crystals,

m.p. 95°, yield 50%. The compound is soluble in 10% NaOH solution and gives no colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃.

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